

TOBARR Test Coding Evaluation Indicator

Q+D no	Level 3 (3 pt)	Level 2 (2 pt)	Level 1 (1 pt)	Level 0 (0 pt)	Considerations in choosing the detentions	Measures to apply with RRs	Application-Types of knowledge
1.1 2.1 3.1 4.1	-Identify in an extended manner all the characteristics of the phenomenon (coding and explicit inference) -Put forward three or more well-founded hypotheses relevant to the phenomenon	- refer to all characteristics (inference coding) -Put forward 1-2 well-founded and relevant hypotheses for the phenomenon	- Identify some of the characteristics) partial coding(-Put forward one hypothesis without a relevant scientific basis for the phenomenon	- The degree of use of cognitive operations of coding and inference as a fundamental condition in identifying the phenomenon -Bringing up possible explanations for the phenomenon/problem indicates the level of scientific knowledge -No reference to the information items in the representation at all -Identify characteristics that are not relevant to understanding the phenomenon	-The degree of use of cognitive operations of coding and inference as a fundamental condition in identifying the problem/phenomenon -Bringing up possible explanations for the phenomenon indicates the level of scientific knowledge	Coding and inference	SMK- Subject Matter Knowledge + Procedural knowledge
1.2 2.2 3.2 4.2	Identified a relations/high ratio to RR	Determined two relations or more	Identified one connection. Determined two relations or more.	No identifying any connections or indicating incorrect or unfounded relations (yes/no).	identifying the number and type of connections (low or high order) indicates understanding the phenomenon and the application level of RR skills.	Identifying relations	SMK-Conceptual knowledge
2.3 3.3 4.3	In a graphical representation or two different graphical representations (continuous/discrete), a graphical representation of the	representing two or more relations between variables	Representation of one relation between two variables -Representing types of graphs (continuous/discrete) without specifying the variables	-No representation -Wrong representation that is not adapted to the phenomenon	A graphic representation of the level of relations (connections) indicates the level of thinking in understanding the phenomenon.	Graphic representation of relations (connections) in the phenomenon verbally or visually	Knowledge representation

	highest pattern of RR relations ('ratio on ratio').		or with only one variable				
1.3 2.4 3.4 4.4	Mapping a pattern of high relations, using a thinking language appropriate for one (or more) RR skills which is the critical skill for understanding the phenomenon	Identify a scientific principle while using thinking language suitable for one RR skill to identify an essential scientific principle of the phenomenon	Identify a scientific principle without using thinking language appropriate for RR skill, or use thinking language for RR without specifying a scientific principle.	No identify a scientific principle and did not use a language of thinking for RR.	-Identify RR relations pattern explicitly by using unique thinking language appropriate for RR skill for the indication (such as -, unusual, differences, similar, different, similarity, difference, contrast, classification into categories, etc.).	Mapping a RR pattern to explain the scientific principle	SMK -Subject Matter Knowledge + Procedural knowledge
1.4 2.5 3.5 4.5	Identify 3-4 relevant RR skills to apply	Identify two relevant RR skills to apply	Identify an appropriate RR skill to apply	-No recognize a RR skill -Mismatched the skill Guess based on a definition without explicit application. - Specify another skill (not RRs).	Explicit meta-strategic awareness is essential for monitoring and controlling the teachers' thought processes about the RR skill they applied .by stating its explicit name	Naming the RR skill (what skill)	MSK-Meta strategic knowledge
1.5 2.6 3.6 4.6	Specify considerations for the application of 3 or more skills suitable for application in the given phenomenon	Specify considerations for the application of two appropriate skills in the context of the given phenomenon	Specify appropriate considerations for one appropriate RR skill.	did not specify the judgments. -Guessed the definition (given in the questionnaire) but did not apply the skill -Explain the skills otherwise	Explicit meta-strategic awareness is essential for monitoring and controlling the teachers' thinking processes - when and why	Justification for using the RR skill (when and why)	MSK-Conditional knowledge + Declarative knowledge